

April 25, 2025

Press release

On 24th March 2025, CIEMAT, in collaboration with the CST4ALL consortium, hosted a successful online R&I workshop on Future Energy Mix with 100% decarbonisation level.

The workshop, attended by more than 150 unique participants from research, industry and governmental organisations, addressed within two sessions main challenges and opportunities to the most relevant renewable technologies to achieve the full decarbonisation target, with special focus on the role and potential of CST (Concentrating Solar Thermal) technologies to contribute to such final objective.

After a welcome from project coordinator (Dr. Peter Heller, DLR, Germany), Ms. Marina Montero (Policy Officer for Solar Thermal Energy at the European Commission) presented the current EU policy landscape and R&I opportunities for Solar Thermal in the context of current Greenhouse Gas Emissions Reduction, highlighting Solar Thermal as one of eight strategic technologies included in the Net Zero Industry Act. The opening session continued with Dr. Hande Eryilmaz of ODTÜ-GÜNAM presenting the ongoing public opinion survey on the Green Deal Challenges and SSH (Social Science and Humanities) and gender aspects researched within the project.

Dr. Julian Blanco (CIEMAT-PSA, Spain) moderated main sessions of the event starting with the keynote presentations of Dr. Johan Lilliestam (Professor for Sustainability Transition Policy at the University Erlangen-Nürnberg), with the topic “CSP: a solution looking for a problem”; Dr. Javier Bonilla (senior researcher at CIEMAT-PSA, Spain), with the topic “Optimizing the Electricity Mix with AI: Application to the Spanish Grid”; and Dr. Peter Nitz (Head of the High Temperature Solar Thermal and Industrial Processes Dept. at Fraunhofer ISE, Germany), with the topic “Paths to a Climate-Neutral Energy System in Germany”.

The second technical session was formed by a roundtable with additional experts (Cristina Trueba, Chair of CST Implementation Working Group; Pedro Horta, Head of the Renewable Energies Chair at the University of Evora, Portugal; Alberto Crespo, Director of Project Development at ENERGYNEST; and Richard Thonig, senior consultant). These experts discussed the main aspects of the current context and future perspectives of the market and policies related to challenges to achieve the full decarbonisation of energy systems, with the focus on the role of CST technologies. Additionally, a poll was conducted among the audience, which identified the main obstacles hindering the deployment of CST technologies in Europe and worldwide.

The key points to draw from the workshop are as follows:

- Future energy systems will have a clear focus on direct electrification in all sectors, with heat pumps and battery electric vehicles as the central technologies, therefore requiring expansion and improvement of electricity grids. Hydrogen will be used mainly in the industrial sector.

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the European Union**

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- CSP (Power production by CST) has not yet found its role within the power system. The technology is still alive and growing, with about 3-4 GW reportedly under development and construction in China, with 800 MW completed and another 24 projects reported as under construction.
- Today CSP is an enabling technology of PV and Wind as on-site hybrid storage/saver (Chinese policy requiring storage connected to PV and Wind projects, being CSP a technology fully suitable for such storage). The alternative to large-scale batteries to enable PV and Wind technologies is still uncertain.
- CSP Tower technologies are dominant today in power production and parabolic troughs in industrial heat applications.
- The market alone will not achieve full decarbonisation, and key policies will be needed to achieve the goal.
- Projections and performed simulations show significant difficulties in achieving 100% of decarbonisation. The relevance of CST contribution to energy systems clearly appears to facilitate the achievement of high levels of decarbonisation in energy systems.

CST4ALL Coordinator

Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt
German Aerospace Center

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow-us on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://twitter.com/Cst4All>
- Website: <https://cst4all.eu/en/>

You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

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